

Welcome

The Precision Agriculture Association of New Zealand (PAANZ) invites you to the 2017 PA-Event in Hamilton, New Zealand.

The event is a marketplace for researchers, practitioners, service and support organisations, to meet, discuss, influence and learn. It includes the *7th Asian-Australasian Conference on Precision Agriculture (7ACPA)*, the *1st Asian-Australasian Conference on Precision Pasture and Livestock Farming (1ACPLF)*, and *Digital Farmer and Grower 2017*.

In plenary sessions more than 20 renowned keynote speakers from all over the world offer attendees their exciting views on precision agriculture and its use. An industry exhibition offers possibilities to see and discuss products and services that are presented by companies from New Zealand and beyond.

PA17 attendee registration provides open access to the total conference programme.

REGISTRATION NOW OPEN

PA17 – The International Tri-Conference for Precision Agriculture in 2017

1ACPLF
PA Science for Pastures & Livestock

1st Asian-Australasian Conference on Precision Pastures & Livestock Farming

7ACPA
PA Science for Crops & Soils

7th Asian-Australasian Conference on Precision Agriculture

DF&G 2017
Adaptation & Adoption of PA

Digital Farmer & Grower 2017

For more information regarding the conference, sponsorship opportunities and collaborating with organisers, please contact us at conference@fp2.co.nz

Precision Agriculture Association New Zealand
TECHNOLOGY FOR SUSTAINABLE GROWTH

Precision Agriculture Association New Zealand

Conference Series

The conference series has a history dating back to 2005 and has been held on six previous occasions. In 2017 the 7th ACPA will be held in Hamilton, New Zealand.

POST CONFERENCE TOURS

Two post conference tours will be offered commencing Thursday 19 October:

North Island

The tour will visit the central North Island, including Hamilton, Tauranga, Rotorua, Taupo and the Hawke's Bay. This tour will offer the attendee a variety of farming, viticulture, horticulture and agritech visits.

South Island

The South Island tour starts and ends in Christchurch, visiting the central South Island, a robotic dairy system, precision arable production, variable rate irrigation, and new fertiliser product technology.

Full conference information including programme, post conference tours and registration details are available at www.7apca-2017.org

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- 7th Asian-Australasian Conference on Precision Agriculture
- 1st Asian-Australasian Conference on Precision Pastures and Livestock Farming
- Digital Farmer and Grower 2017

Monday 16 - Wednesday 18 October 2017

CLAUDELANDS CONFERENCE AND EXHIBITION CENTRE, HAMILTON

www.7acpa-2017.org

www.7acpa-2017.org

7th Asian-Australasian Conference on Precision Agriculture (7ACPA)

The ACPA is one of three international Precision Agriculture conferences that are conducted biannually as part of a series – each held in different locations around the world.

At the ACPA, world-leading scientists will present and discuss the research and development of Precision Agriculture in the Asian-Australasian region and around the world.

The Conference will include field trips to view practical examples of ongoing precision agriculture and horticulture in New Zealand.

New Zealand offers spectacular landscapes and extraordinary opportunities to see diverse and first class agricultural production systems which are highly profitable.

In collaboration with the 7th ACPA, the Society of Precision Agriculture Australia (SPAA) will be joining us with a symposium on arable production using Precision Agriculture.

Presentations from our keynote presenters will include: A world view, diversity and advancement, automisation, hands-free robot fields, proximal and remote crop sensing.

1st Asian-Australasian Conference on Precision Pasture and Livestock Farming (1ACPLF)

The Precision Agriculture Association of New Zealand is pleased to announce the 1st Asian-Australasian Conference on Precision Pasture and Livestock Farming, to be held in conjunction with the 7ACPA.

Precision Pasture and Livestock Farming (ACPLF) represents knowledge and tools for managing pastures and animals.

Farmers can measure pasture growth or monitor animal welfare, health and productivity with digital tools from ACPLF. Such tools can also assess the environmental impact from livestock. New Zealand and Australian agritech research and commercial organisations have a strong history of innovation in this space and farmers are proven adopters and leaders in the related farming systems.

The 1ACPLF will succeed the Australian New Zealand symposium series on Spatially Enabled Livestock Management and introduce additional topics.

Presentations from our keynote speakers will include: What can we learn from use of developing countries, precision medicine, what can it offer, benefits, limitations and expectation to animal based farm information management systems.

Digital Farmer and Grower 2017

DF&G2017

Digital Farmer and Grower (DF&G2017) is a conference, dedicated to farmers, growers, their consultants and counterparts in service and support organisations of the primary sector. DF&G2017 will cover a range of needs of farmers and growers to be informed of the latest developments and application of precision agriculture. This conference offers unique ways to grow the network of people interested in practical adaptation of precision agriculture technologies in New Zealand, Australia, Asia and beyond.

The main focus of DF&G2017 is to demonstrate how to adapt precision agriculture technologies for use in production systems. This will also address how practitioners can meet growing demands of consumers by the use of precision technologies and ensure future sustainability.

Three sessions over two days are covering the precision agriculture adaptation and use for 'Permanent Crops', 'Arable Crops' and 'Pastures and Livestock'. A fourth session addresses the ways precision agriculture already helps farmers and growers to produce 'within limits'.

Farmers and growers present their experience, panel discussions allow for drilling deep into critical points and informal meetings offer chances to interact with the speakers and the panel members.